

A mixture design approach to investigate the impact of raw and processed chickpea flour on the techno-functional properties in a bakery application[☆]

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ABSTRACT

Legumes, particularly chickpeas (*Cicer arietinum* L.), are recognized for their exceptional nutritional value, and their inclusion in diets is widely encouraged by global health organizations, including the World Health Organization. Given their longstanding use in traditional recipes such as *Farinata* or *Socca* (Italian chickpea pancake), *Panella* (Sicilian chickpea fritter) etc. integrating chickpea flour into bakery products offers an effective strategy for enhancing legume consumption. This study focused on the development of chickpea flour-fortified sponge cakes using varying proportions (0–50 %) of raw chickpea flour (CPF), microwave-roasted chickpea flour (MRCPF), heat moisture-treated chickpea flour (HMC PF), using wheat flour (WF) as the base flour and control formulation. A simplex lattice mixture design was employed to optimize the flour blend for improved techno-functional and nutritional properties of the sponge cake. Key parameters such as specific cake volume, crumb hardness, crumb colour [L* (lightness) and b* (yellowness)], slice brightness, and protein content were analysed. The optimal formulation consisted of 71 % WF, 1.04 % CPF, 15.46 % MRCPF, and 12.5 % HMC PF. The optimized sponge cake exhibited a specific volume of 2.05 (ml/g), crumb hardness of 6.34 N, crumb L* of 72.52, crumb b* of 28.96, slice brightness of 98.2, and protein content of 11.17 %, achieving a desirability index of 0.894. This study highlights the potential for using chickpea flour variants to develop nutritionally enriched bakery products with desirable technical and functional characteristics.

1. Introduction

Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) is a globally cultivated legume, renowned for its exceptional nutritional profile and adaptability in various culinary contexts. It is a cost-effective source of plant-based protein, containing approximately 20–22 % protein, which surpasses the protein content of most cereal grains (R. R. Kaur & Prasad, 2021). Chickpea production has steadily increased worldwide, reflecting its growing significance. For instance, global chickpea production rose from 11.6 Mt in 2016 to 15.1 Mt in 2017, as reported by United Nations Food and Agriculture Organization Statistical Database (FAOSTAT) (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/>). In Europe, there is an increasing prevalence of flexitarian, vegan, and vegetarian dietary preferences, significantly influencing the demand for plant-based products (Derbyshire, 2017; European Commission D.-G. for A. and R. D, 2019). This transition aligns with production data, which shows an increase in chickpea

production in the European region from 83452.42 t in 2016–143253.95 t in 2017 according to the FAOSTAT (<https://www.fao.org/faostat/>).

Chickpeas are valued for their high protein bioavailability, biological value, well-balanced amino acid profile and good functional properties (Grasso et al., 2022). Traditionally chickpea is consumed in the form of hummus, fermented foods, and other regional preparations (Ahmed et al., 2020; Alsalman et al., 2022; Chandra-Hioe et al., 2016). They are now extensively utilized in developing innovative food products such as plant-based meat alternatives, dairy substitutes, protein-rich snacks, and gluten-free baked goods (Boukid, 2021; Duarte et al., 2022; Khvostenko et al., 2024; Talens et al., 2023; Vinod et al., 2023).

Extensive studies on the incorporation of chickpea flour in cakes (Bravo-Núñez & Gómez, 2023; Gómez et al., 2008; Krause et al., 2022) support the use of raw chickpea flour due to its high protein content (~21.9–26.8 %), excellent protein digestibility (76–78 %), and its functional properties, which collectively enhance the nutritional value

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Table 1
Proximate composition, visual colour and particle size analysis of plain wheat flour, raw chickpea flour, roasted chickpea flour and heat moisture treated chickpea flour used for cake preparation.

Flour	Proximate composition			Colour Parameters			Particle size characteristics						
	Moisture (%)	Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Ash (%)	Resistant Starch (%)	L*	a*	b*	D[3,2] (µm)	D[4,3] (µm)	Dv10 (µm)	Dv50 (µm)	Dv90 (µm)
WF	13.50 ± 0.02 ^d	12.25 ± 0.22 ^a	0.83 ± 0.17 ^a	1.04 ± 0.11 ^a	2.10 ± 0.27 ^a	55.10 ± 0.07 ^a	-0.28 ± 0.07 ^a	6.48 ± 0.07 ^a	54.66 ± 3.77 ^a	86.63 ± 4.21 ^a	26.20 ± 2.19 ^a	82.96 ± 6.50 ^a	151.33 ± 4.04 ^a
CPF	11.04 ± 0.03 ^c	22.50 ± 0.20 ^b	6.23 ± 0.01 ^c	4.12 ± 0.35 ^b	3.01 ± 0.16 ^a	53.64 ± 6.49 ^a	-0.41 ± 0.04 ^a	18.63 ± 0.67 ^b	54.00 ± 2.93 ^a	124.66 ± 2.08 ^b	25.66 ± 1.79 ^a	77.13 ± 6.37 ^a	299.00 ± 13.74 ^b
MRCPF	2.96 ± 0.07 ^a	22.80 ± 0.03 ^b	6.28 ± 0.16 ^c	4.26 ± 0.18 ^b	4.60 ± 1.80 ^a	44.43 ± 2.19 ^a	3.59 ± 0.34 ^c	17.67 ± 0.77 ^b	56.63 ± 6.04 ^a	125.33 ± 12.01 ^b	26.86 ± 2.34 ^a	83.93 ± 13.32 ^a	290.66 ± 15.53 ^b
HMC PF	4.00 ± 0.13 ^b	22.45 ± 0.05 ^b	3.89 ± 0.01 ^b	4.18 ± 0.13 ^b	9.63 ± 0.61 ^b	55.12 ± 3.62 ^a	1.26 ± 0.05 ^b	18.11 ± 0.91 ^b	69.23 ± 3.32 ^b	164.66 ± 8.73 ^c	30.53 ± 0.90 ^b	121.33 ± 12.42 ^b	367.66 ± 15.56 ^c

WF=Plain Wheat Flour; CPF=Raw Chickpea Flour; MRCPF = Microwave roasted chickpea flour; HMC PF=Heat moisture treated chickpea flour; Dv10, Dv50, and Dv90 represent the hydrodynamic diameters at which 10 %, 50 %, and 90 % of the sample particles, respectively, are smaller than the corresponding diameter values.

of the product (Alvarez et al., 2017; Kahraman et al., 2022). Despite its nutritional advantages, incorporating chickpea flour into wheat-based formulations presents several challenges (Bravo-Núñez & Gómez, 2023). The reduction in gluten content caused by partial wheat substitution in bread formulations negatively impacts the rheological behaviour of bread dough which, in turn, negatively impacts the volume, hardness and taste attributes of the product (Nkurikiye et al., 2023). Additionally, chickpea derived flours are often associated with undesirable flavour profiles, such as "beany," "earthy," or "bitter" notes, which can affect sensory acceptance (Kotsiou et al., 2022). To overcome these challenges, several pre-processing methods such as soaking, thermal treatments, germination, and fermentation have been proposed to improve the functional and sensory properties of legume flours (Chigwedere et al., 2022). Among these, roasting has shown promise in reducing off-flavours by generating desirable volatile compounds such as pyrazines, while also enhancing sensory appeal (Garvey et al., 2021; Kotsiou et al., 2023; Roland et al., 2017). Recent studies have demonstrated the potential of roasted chickpea flours in improving flavour profiles. For instance, wheat biscuits fortified with roasted and germinated chickpea flour exhibited satisfactory sensory characteristics (Saeed et al., 2023). Additionally, wheat bread substituted with 10 % roasted chickpea flour by Kotsiou et al. (2022) was able to mask completely the "grass-like" flavour with reduced "beany" and "earthy" off-flavour notes in breads.

Heat-moisture treatment (HMT) modifies flour functionality by altering the granular structure of starch, improving viscoelastic properties and increasing the availability of phenolic compounds (Zhang et al., 2023). Microwaves have enabled a reduction in processing time and energy consumption while preserving organoleptic properties via rapid moisture evaporation (Kutlu et al., 2022). Applying roasting and HMT combined with microwave radiation, has demonstrated a synergistic effect, enhancing functional properties such as water-holding and oil-binding capacities, while also improving bread-making performance in gluten-free formulations (Lisovska et al., 2023; Najib et al., 2023). It is important to note that raw chickpea flour contains several anti-nutritional factors that can hinder nutrient absorption and digestion. Processing techniques such as roasting and heat-moisture treatment have been shown to effectively mitigate these anti-nutritional factors, improving the overall nutritional profile of chickpea-based products (Ma et al., 2011). However, due to the scope of the current experimental design, it was not possible to include an analysis of these aspects. Future studies will address sensory data, shelf-life analysis, or broader nutritional assessment (e.g., amino acid profile) of chickpea flour based cake formulations.

This study aims to explore the incorporation of raw and processed chickpea flours, including microwave assisted heat moisture treated and roasted chickpea flour, into wheat-based composite sponge cake formulations a novel approach that has not been extensively studied. The research focuses on optimizing flour ratios to achieve desirable baking qualities such as specific volume, crumb hardness, crumb colour, slice brightness, and protein content, while mitigating structural defects. By integrating advanced flour processing techniques, this work seeks to fill the gap in developing nutritionally enhanced bakery products with improved textural properties, offering new insights into the potential of chickpea flour in bakery formulations.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Raw materials

The following ingredients were used to formulate the sponge cake batter: chickpea flour (Beotronics, Ireland), soft wheat flour (Shackleton, Ireland), margarine (purchased locally), water, granulated sugar (purchased locally), fresh whole eggs (purchased locally), and sodium bicarbonate (purchased locally).

Table 2

Experimental design and mass fraction of eighteen flour components according to simplex lattice mixture design and responses.

RUN	A: WF (g)	B:CPF (g)	C:MRCPF (g)	D:HMCPF (g)	Specific Volume (ml/g)	Crumb Hardness (N)	Crumb L*	Crumb b*	Slice Brightness	Protein Content (%)
15	284.375	21.875	21.875	21.875	2.32	4.80	74.92	25.49	109.8	10.05
6	284.375	21.875	21.875	21.875	2.17	5.83	74.92	26.75	109.2	10.70
2	175	175	0	0	2.2	5.47	73.23	27.99	107.7	11.41
11	175	175	0	0	2.23	5.47	75.80	26.93	105.7	11.60
1	350	0	0	0	2.03	6.67	72.65	25.73	111	9.25
10	350	0	0	0	2.09	6.56	74.08	24.34	113.5	9.27
9	196.875	21.875	21.875	109.375	2.08	5.23	66.54	28.96	90.0	11.28
18	196.875	21.875	21.875	109.375	2.05	4.93	65.97	29.53	89.8	11.41
4	175	0	0	175	2.05	4.19	63.71	31.30	81.8	11.50
13	175	0	0	175	2.07	4.22	64.98	30.41	83.2	11.11
14	218.75	43.75	43.75	43.75	2.28	4.52	70.41	27.88	100.5	10.88
5	218.75	43.75	43.75	43.75	2.26	4.47	66.12	28.90	98.6	11.18
17	196.875	21.875	109.375	21.875	2.22	5.33	65.17	28.32	97.7	11.35
8	196.875	21.875	109.375	21.875	2.19	5.38	64.16	28.17	97.9	10.51
3	175	0	175	0	1.93	8.73	66.13	29.21	95.8	11.62
12	175	0	175	0	1.94	8.69	66.15	29.75	93.8	11.64
7	196.875	109.375	21.875	21.875	2.19	5.21	64.60	26.02	102.0	11.79
16	196.875	109.375	21.875	21.875	2.21	5.57	66.59	26.20	102.5	11.25

2.1.1. Microwave treatment

For roasting, the chickpea flour was initially exposed to microwave radiation at the maximum available power (1000 W) in a microwave Inverter (Panasonic, Ireland). Roasting of chickpea flour was performed in 500g batches under continuous stirring to ensure uniform thermal treatment for ~1 min. The chickpea flour was roasted for 8 min. The initial moisture content of the flour was 12.14 % and after microwave roasting it decreased by 1.50 %.

For heat moisture treatment of the chickpea flour the initial moisture content of the flour was adjusted to ~30 % and kept overnight at refrigerated temperature to equilibrate the moisture content of the flour and then exposed to microwave radiation at the maximum available power (1000 W) in a microwave Inverter (Panasonic, Ireland). The electromagnetic radiation was applied intermittently in short periods of 60 s. The total treatment time was 8 min with constant mixing. After treatment, the samples were collected and stored at 4 °C for further analysis. The soft wheat flour was passed through 125 µm mesh sieve and all processed flours and the raw chickpea flour was passed through 400 µm mesh sieve.

2.2. Physicochemical analysis of flours

The total proximate composition of wheat flour, chickpea flour, and composite flours formulated based on the mixture design was assessed. Moisture content was measured following method 44–15.02 (AACC, n. d.). Protein content was determined using the combustion method based on the Dumas principle with LECO equipment (FP-628, LECO Corp., USA), employing a nitrogen conversion factor (Nx5.7) as per method 968.06 (AOAC, 2000). Fat content was analysed using the ORACLE Rapid NMR Fat Analyser (CEM Corp., USA) in accordance with AOAC (1991). Ash content was determined with a Gallenkamp Muffle Furnace using pre-drying at 550 °C as outlined in method 08–01.01 (Gallenkamp, UK; AACC, n.d.). Resistant Starch Assay Kit (AACC Method 32–40.01, AACC, 2000), respectively, from Megazyme (Wicklow, Ireland). The results of protein, fat, resistant starch and ash were corrected for moisture content and reported on a g/100 g dry matter (DM) basis. Particle size analysis was conducted using laser diffraction through the Aero S dry dispersion unit of a Mastersizer 3000 (Malvern Instruments Ltd, UK). The procedure followed McSweeney et al. (2020) with slight adjustments in air pressure (ranging from 2.5 to 4.0 bar) and feed rate (50–100 %), contingent on sample flowability. Scanning electron micrographs were collected using SEM (Supra 40VP, ZEISS,

Germany) equipped with a secondary electron detector at 2 kV accelerating voltage.

2.3. Experimental design

A Simplex-lattice centroid mixture design with 2 replicates of the whole design was employed to optimize the formulation for chickpea fortified sponge cake with four individual variables which were soft wheat flour (WF), chickpea flour (CPF), microwave roasted chickpea flour (MRCPF) and heat moisture treated chickpea flour (HMCPF). The upper and lower limits for these components were: A: 50–100 %, B: 0–50 %, C: 0–50 %, and D: 0–50 %, respectively. Previous studies have reported increased adhesiveness in cakes formulated with 100 % chickpea flour, while sensory evaluations indicated acceptable overall palatability only up to a 50 % inclusion level (Gallego et al., 2022; Gómez et al., 2008). Based on these findings, the incorporation of chickpea flour was limited to a maximum of 50 % in the current study's simplex-lattice mixture design to ensure desirable textural and sensory qualities in the final product. Eighteen experiments were derived from the Minitab program. Specific volume (SV), crumb hardness, crumb L*, crumb b*, and slice brightness served as the responses. The experimental results from the trials performed according to the Simplex-lattice centroid mixture design are tabulated in Table 2. These results are given as input in Design Expert software for mixture design analysis. The regression analysis was conducted using a quadratic and linear model to describe the relationship between the proportions of the mixture components and the responses. The formulation design points or 3D plots and corresponding compositions can be found in supplementary data (Fig. 1.) and Table 2.

2.4. Batter and sponge cake preparation

The required quantities of the primary ingredients, wheat flour, chickpea flour, roasted chickpea flour and heat moisture treated chickpea flour, were weighed and blended according to the mixture design. A control sponge cake formulation was used as per (Milner et al., 2020) with the flour blend comprising WF, CPF, MRCPF and HMCPF. The sponge cake batter was mixed using Kenwood (UK) mixer. In a mixing bowl, flour (35.5 %), sugar (19.5 %), egg (16 %), water (12.4 %), margarine (16 %), and sodium bicarbonate (0.7 %) were combined and mixed on speed 1 for 30 s. The bowl was scraped and the batter was further mixed at speed (2) for 2 min. A pup loaf tin (80 mm × 60 mm x

Fig. 1. Particle size distribution and Micrographs [SEM ($\times 500$)] of flour samples used in cake formulation. WF: Soft wheat flour, CPF: Raw chickpea flour, MRCPF: Microwave roasted chickpea flour, HMCPF: Heat moisture treated chickpea flour.

40 mm) was scaled with 80g of sponge cake batter and baked in a conventional oven (Macpan MDBt8, Thiene, Italy) at 180 °C for 45 min. The sponge cakes were stored at room temperature until cool and then packed into polyethylene bags and stored overnight. The experimental design was undertaken as outlined in Table 2.

2.5. Sponge cake analysis

2.5.1. Specific volume

The specific volume of each sponge cake was calculated as the ratio of their measured volume to weight. For each treatment cakes were randomly selected and analysed on the day of baking 3 h post baking. Measurements were conducted using a TexVol instrument (BV-L370, Sweden), with the sponge cakes positioned vertically during the assessment.

2.5.2. Crumb internal structure

Crumb structural properties were evaluated one day post-baking. Each sponge cake was halved vertically, and a 1 cm-thick slice was obtained from both halves. The samples were scanned using a C-Cell digital imaging analyser (Calibre Instruments Ltd., Warrington, UK) integrated with specialized software for analysis. Key parameters such as slice brightness, slice dimensions (area, height, width), cell characteristics (number of cells, holes, average diameter, wall thickness), and distribution patterns (coarse vs. fine clusters, cell elongation) were recorded.

2.5.3. Crumb colour

The L^* (a scale of 0 = black and 100 = white), a^* (a negative value indicates greenness and a positive value indicates redness), and b^* (a negative value is blueness and positive value is yellowness) colour

values of the sponge cake crust and crumb were measured using a Chroma Meter CR-410 (Konica Minolta, UK), calibrated with a standardized white reference tile. For each treatment, ten measurements were taken from the top surface of the crust and ten from the crumb on the first day 3 h post-baking.

2.5.4. Crumb texture

Crumb textural properties as hardness, including springiness, resilience, and cohesiveness were assessed through texture profile analysis. Two 1 cm - thick vertical slices were taken from the centre of each sponge cake. Using a TAXT2i Texture Analyser, tests were performed with a strain level of 40 % of the slice height at a speed of 1 mm/s, with a trigger force set at 0.049 N.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All tests were replicated three times and mean values and standard deviations were calculated. The effects of treatment of the chickpea flour on the physicochemical properties of the resulting sponge cakes were determined using analysis of variance (ANOVA) using XLSTAT 2023 software (AddinSoft™ S.A.R.L., Paris, France) (<https://www.xlstat.com/en>). To determine significant differences between means, the Fisher Least Significant Difference test (LSD) was performed at a 5 % probability level ($p < 0.05$). The design was developed using Minitab (Minitab® 21), mathematical modelling and graphical presentations (ternary contour plots, response surface plots) were performed using a statistical package design expert version StatEase (Design-Expert v23.0, Stat-Ease Inc., Minneapolis, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Physicochemical characterisation of raw and treated flour ingredients

The proximate composition and colour parameters of wheat flour (WF), raw chickpea flour (CPF), microwave roasted chickpea flour (MRCPF) and heat moisture treated chickpea flour (HMC PF) are summarized in Table 1. Moisture contents of WF, CPF, MRCPF and HMC PF were 13.50, 11.05, 2.96 and 4.03 %, respectively. A significant difference in moisture content between all flours was observed. As expected MRCPF showed the lowest moisture content among all flours. This could be due to microwave roasting conditions, as microwaves penetrate the flour particles by causing water molecules to vibrate and move due to the pressure gradient allowing rapid evaporation of moisture (Sruthi et al., 2021). The protein content of MRCPF, HMC PF, and raw CPF was notably higher than that of the control wheat flour, with all chickpea flour samples having a higher protein content in comparison to the control wheat flour. The HMC PF showed significant reduction in fat content than that of CPF and MRCPF (6.23 and 6.28 %). Ash content of the CPF, RCPF and HMC PF of samples showed no significant difference. However all samples were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in ash compared with the control flour.

The colour of the ingredients specifically flours, used for baking directly affects the colour of the resulting products. The a^* (redness/greenness) and b^* (yellowness/blueness) values of the flours showed significant difference (Table 1). In addition, a^* and b^* were statistically different ($p < 0.05$) among the four samples. This could be due to heat treatment involved in roasting and heat-moisture treatment which initiates development of brown pigments due to Maillard reaction influences the colour properties of flour (Jogihalli, Singh, Kumar, & Sharanagat, 2017). Positive values for a^* indicate more of a red undertone, and negative values indicate colours that are closer to a green hue. Regarding the b^* value, increasingly positive values for b^* indicates more of a yellow than blue undertone. Also, CPF, HMC PF, MRCPF flours had the highest values (18.635, 18.115 and 17.675) in comparison to the wheat control (6.480). Previous studies have also reported a yellow

colour of raw chickpea flour (Sidhu et al., 2024).

The resistant starch content of the soft wheat flour was 2.10 % which is in agreement with the previously reported results (Lu & Baik, 2015). Heat-moisture treatment of chickpea flour was shown to significantly increase the resistant starch (RS) content from 3.008 to 9.630 %. This increase indicates that structural interactions, such as those between amylose–amylose and/or amylose–amylopectin chains, form during the treatment process and remain intact even after subsequent gelatinization. These interactions likely contribute to reduced enzymatic accessibility by limiting the hydrolysis of starch chains, thereby enhancing resistance to digestion. Such structural modifications are also attributed to the rearrangement of starch molecules during the treatment, which reinforces their resistance to enzymatic breakdown (Chung et al., 2009). The increase in RS content within the flour translated into higher RS levels in the resulting sponge cakes, thereby improving their dietary fiber composition, which plays a vital role in maintaining gut health and lowering the risk of metabolic diseases, including diabetes and cardiovascular disorders (Segundo et al., 2017).

The particle size distribution of the flours is presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1. The four flours showed an average particle diameter Dv_{50} from 77.13 μm for CPF, 82.96 μm for WF, 83.93 μm for MRCPF to 121.33 μm for HMC PF. It is important to note that for heat-moisture treated chickpea flour, the Dv_{90} was 367.667 μm , indicating that the HMC PF contains coarse particles that were significantly higher than the other 3 flours ($p < 0.05$). On average, the size of fine particles ($D[3,2]$) were similar among WF, CPF and MRCPF, but significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) for the HMC PF. These differences between the treated and untreated chickpea flour may be due to the aggregation of starch granules and adhesion of other substances to the starch owing to the partial gelatinization of the starch granules during heat-moisture treatment (M. Kaur et al., 2019; Li et al., 2024).

The wheat flour samples depicted an almost bimodal distribution with a prominent first mode around 25 μm . Commonly in soft wheat varieties, the particle size distribution shows a prominent first mode around 25 μm , which corresponds mainly to isolated starch granules. This mode is less pronounced or absent in hard wheat varieties (Devaux et al., 1998). All chickpea flour samples showed a bimodal distribution with two sharp peak around >50 and < 100 μm .

Scanning electron micrographs of flour samples are presented in Fig. 1. The wheat flour samples displayed starch granules of different sizes and shapes (spherical and oval). These granules are attached to the gluten or protein matrix. As found in chickpea starch granules by Ynestrá Marure et al. (2019), raw chickpea flour displayed lenticular-shaped starch granules of varying sizes. Microwave treatment showed no major changes to the chickpea flour starch granules. The starch granules were generally more uniformly distributed in the microwave roasted chickpea flour matrix than the raw chickpea flour. The heat-moisture treatment partially gelatinised the starch granules and aggregates were observed. Similar partial gelatinization and agglomeration of starch granules for heat-moisture treated wheat starches at higher moisture content was observed by (Wang et al., 2023).

3.2. Effect of mixture design on physical and functional properties of sponge cake

3.2.1. Mixture design modelling: effect on specific volume of sponge cake

The specific volume of sponge cake is influenced by the amount of air incorporated into the batter and the capacity of the batter to hold this air. The incorporation of legume flour in a sponge cake formulation may affect the specific volume of the sponge cake as legume flours are rich in proteins (e.g. globulins and albumins) and starches that interact differently to wheat constituents. Legume proteins can stabilize the air cells in the batter, which may help retain gases during baking, potentially increasing or maintaining the specific volume of the sponge cake (Gómez et al., 2008, 2012). However, excessive substitution with legume flours can lead to reduced specific volume and collapse of the

Fig. 2. The contour plots (the dots in contour plots indicate the response value at the corresponding ratios of the mixtures), the response surfaces obtained via fitting to the model, and the differences between the predicted and experimental response value for the responses a) SV, b) Crumb Hardness, c) Crumb L*, d) Crumb b*, e) Slice brightness f) Protein content. The predicted values are equal to the experimental values along the perfect prediction line. (Alphabets A, B, C, and D in contour plots stand for wheat flour, chickpea flour, microwave roasted chickpea flour, and heat moisture treated chickpea flour respectively; D is fixed at 43.75).

sponge cake structure due to the reduced ability of the batter to trap air, which is essential for sponge cake rise and uniformity (Gómez et al., 2012).

The quadratic model passed all the selection criteria, and was found to be significant in accessing the interaction between soft wheat flour (A), chickpea flour (B), microwave roasted chickpea flour (C) and heat-moisture treated chickpea flour (D). The F-values and p-values for the studied quadratic model were 14.98 and 0.0001, respectively. The details relating to the statistical estimates, such as R^2 value, adjusted R^2 , and adequate precision, are shown in Table 3. The equation predicting interactions between the individual components for the specific volume of the sponge cake is shown in Eq. 1.

Specific Volume = $2.056 A + 1.806 B - 3.393 C + 2.876 D + 1.119 AB + 10.399 AC - 1.639 AD + 0.920 BC$ (Eq. (1))

The coefficients of Eq. (1) indicate that heat-moisture treated chickpea flour (D) has the positive influence on the specific volume of sponge cakes, followed by wheat flour and raw chickpea flour. This is likely due to the superior retention capacity of the heat-moisture treated chickpea flour and enhanced gelatinization properties of the heat-moisture treated samples, which improve its ability to retain gases during baking, thereby increasing the specific volume of sponge cakes (Zhang et al., 2023). The magnitude of each variable's contribution is reflected in the absolute value of its coefficient, while the sign (positive or negative) indicates whether the variable positively or negatively affects the response. The equation predicting specific volume shows positive coefficients for all variables except for the microwave roasted

chickpea flour (MRCPF), where the process negatively impacts the specific volume. These findings align with earlier research showing that bread made with wheat and raw chickpea flour blends achieved greater loaf volume compared to bread made with wheat flour and roasted chickpea flour blends (Baik & Han, 2012).

Eq. (2) can also be presented in the form of a two dimensional contour plot and three dimensional response surface plot as seen in Fig. 2 (a1, and a2). The contour and response surface plot indicate that the specific volume is high towards the wheat flour and microwave roasted chickpea flour vortex when heat-moisture treated chickpea flour value is kept constant at 12.5 % while an increase in the amount of microwave roasted chickpea flour decreased the specific volume of the sponge cakes. The reduction in sponge cake volume observed with the addition of microwave roasted chickpea flour is associated with alterations in the water solubility index and oil absorption capacity, stemming from roasting induced structural changes, including protein denaturation and starch gelatinization (Jogihalli, Singh, & Sharanagat, 2017; Köten, 2021).

A 3D representation Fig. 2. (a2) shows the connection between the independent and dependent variables for visualizing how the specific volume of the sponge cakes changes as the quantities of the three flours (WF, CPF, and MRCPF) are varied and the amount of heat-moisture treated chickpea flour HMCPF was kept constant. These results highlight the critical role of flour selection and formulation in optimizing sponge cake volume. The prediction performances of the mixture experimental design for specific volume of the sponge cakes are shown

Fig. 2. (continued).

in Fig. 2 (a3). The predicted and experimental values for specific volume are well correlated with a R^2 value of 0.913 and adequate precision value of 11.184.

3.2.2. Mixture design modelling: effect on crumb hardness of the sponge cake

In food texture analysis, hardness is quantified as the maximum force recorded during the initial compression phase in a texture profile analysis (TPA) curve. It is a critical parameter used to assess the resistance of a food product to deformation under applied pressure, providing insights into the effort required to achieve the first bite. The quadratic model was found to be effective at accessing the change in the crumb hardness of the sponge cakes. The model produced less noise and a higher F-value (42.62) with higher R^2 (0.967) and adjusted R^2 values (0.944). The lack of fit was insignificant for the model (Table 3). The regression model for the hardness of the composite sponge cakes is shown in Eq. (2). The coefficients of this equation highlight that microwave roasted chickpea flour (C) exerts the most substantial influence on the crumb hardness of the sponge cakes, followed by WF. Conversely, chickpea flour and heat-moisture treated chickpea flour exhibit a negative impact on the hardness of the sponge cakes, indicating their potential to reduce firmness.

Crumb Hardness = 6.645 A - 6.523 B + 52.851 C - 1.024 D + 21.77 AB - 84.02 AC + 5.683 AD - 36.968 BC (Eq. (2))

Substituting wheat flour for raw chickpea flour in sponge cake formulations showed a positive impact on crumb softness. These results agree with those obtained by Campbell et al. (2019) when these authors

included cowpea protein isolate at levels of up to 7.2 % in sponge cake. Further the application of heat-moisture treated chickpea flour also depicted a softer crumb texture of sponge cake likely due to its larger particle size compared to raw chickpea flour and improved thermal stability of the chickpea starch induced by heat-moisture treatment as discussed by Zhang et al. (2023).

The contour and 3D plot [Fig. 2 (b1 and b2)] illustrates that sponge cakes formulated with higher concentrations of microwave roasted chickpea flour exhibited significantly greater crumb hardness values. This observation is in contrast to the effects of raw chickpea flour and heat-moisture treated chickpea flour. This effect can be attributed to restricted starch gelatinization resulting from reduced water availability during the roasting process. Prolonged roasting decreases flour moisture, promotes protein aggregation, and limits starch swelling through protein-starch interactions, ultimately leading to a firmer crumb structure (Gu et al., 2022; Patil et al., 2024; Rothschild et al., 2015). The predicted and experimental values for crumb hardness of the sponge cakes are well correlated [Fig. 2(b3)].

3.2.3. Mixture design modelling: effect on crumb colour (L^* and b^*) of the sponge cake crumb

The interaction between the four different flours and their blends on the colour value (L^* lightness) and (b^* yellowness) of the composite sponge cake samples was calculated with the quadratic model. The predictive equation for the interaction of individual components on sponge cake colour values is represented by Equations. (3) and (4).

Crumb L^* = 73.312 A + 61.337 B - 59.733 C + 53.619 D + 28.56 AB

e1

e2

e3

f1

f2

f3

Fig. 2. (continued).

Table 3

Statistical analysis (ANOVA) and regression coefficient data for chickpea flour fortified sponge cakes.

Variables	Specific Volume (ml/g)	Crumb Hardness (N)	Crumb L*	Crumb b*	Slice Brightness	Protein Content (%)
F-value	14.98	42.62	23.57	13.86	194.16	28.74
p-value	0.0001	<0.0001	<0.0001	0.0002	<0.0001	<0.0001
Lack of fit p-value	0.15	0.07	0.42	0.05	0.54	0.42
Standard deviation	0.04	0.30	1.35	0.74	1.03	0.31
Mean	2.14	5.63	68.68	27.88	99.47	10.99
C.V.%	2.04	5.48	1.97	2.68	1.04	2.86
Press	0.06	2.88	45.35	16.56	36.82	1.39
R ²	0.91	0.96	0.94	0.90	0.99	0.86
Adjusted R ²	0.85	0.94	0.90	0.84	0.98	0.83
Predicted R ²	0.72	0.90	0.86	0.72	0.97	0.79
Adeq Precision	11.18	21.93	12.02	11.66	43.12	15.14

+ 237.200 AC + 3.304 AD - 393.176 BC (Eq. (3))

Crumb b* = 24.968 A + 51.278 B + 19.238 C + 30.147 D - 42.919 AB + 29.239 AC + 12.912 AD - 36.087 BC (Eq. (4))

The positive coefficient of the crumb L* of the sponge cake is 73.312 for cakes formulated with wheat flour followed by 61.337 for raw chickpea flour and 53.619 for heat-moisture treated chickpea flour. This shows that raw chickpea flour and heat-moisture treated chickpea flour incorporation displayed less of an effect on sponge cake light/dark appearance as compared to wheat flour. These findings are in correlation with the earlier findings by (Gómez et al., 2008) who found that 50

% incorporation of chickpea flour had no significant effect on the crumb lightness value of wheat flour-based sponge and layer cakes. Among the flours evaluated, microwave roasted chickpea flour exhibited negative L* value, highlighting its pronounced but adverse impact on crumb lightness, likely due to the darker coloration or brown pigments development due to Maillard reaction during the roasting process (Joghialli, Singh, Kumar, & Sharanagat, 2017).

All flours utilized in the preparation of composite sponge cakes demonstrated a positive impact on the b* value, which is an indication of the yellow/blue undertones of the crumb. Among the flours, raw

Fig. 3. Slice brightness using C-Cell analysis g1) RUN1, g2) RUN2, g3) RUN3, g4) RUN4, g5) RUN5, g6) RUN6, g7) RUN7, g8) RUN8 and g9) RUN9.

chickpea flour exhibited the most significant influence, yielding the highest positive b^* values, while incorporating microwave roasted chickpea flour had the least effect on the crumb colour. The increased b^* value observed with raw chickpea flour addition is likely attributed to its higher β -carotene content compared to WF (Krause et al., 2022). This suggests that the carotenoid composition of the flours plays a critical role in determining the yellowness of the sponge cake crumb. The prediction performances of the mixture experimental design for L^* and a^* are shown in Fig. 2 (c3 and d3), respectively. The predicted and experimental values for both responses are well correlated.

3.2.4. Mixture design modelling: effect on slice brightness of the sponge cake crumb

The brightness of a sponge cake slice is determined by the light reflectance from the crumb calculated with image analysis software associated with C-Cell DIA (Digital Imaging Analysis), with higher brightness values typically indicating a finer crumb texture and a more uniform distribution of air cells. This parameter is essential for evaluating sponge cake quality, as it may influence visual appeal and reflects factors such as ingredient integration, baking conditions, and the influence of flour types or additives used. The quadratic model was identified as the most effective approach for assessing changes in slice brightness, as it demonstrated minimal noise, a high F-value (194.16), and strong statistical reliability with an R^2 value of 0.99 and an adjusted R^2 of 0.988. Additionally, the model's lack of fit was statistically

insignificant (Table 3), indicating its robustness. The regression equation for predicting slice brightness is provided in Eq. (5), reflecting the influence of multiple variables on crumb quality and appearance. The contour plots, 3D plots and slice brightness images captured using C-Cell are presented in Fig. 2. (e1, e2 and e3) and Fig. 3 (g1, g2, g3, g4, g5, g6, g7 and g8) respectively.

Slice brightness = $112.289 A + 49.582 B - 22.217 C + 93.013 D + 103.200 AB + 199.200 AC - 80.460 AD - 167.660 BC$ (Eq. (5))

Soft wheat flour demonstrated the highest positive coefficient for slice brightness, followed by heat-moisture treated chickpea flour and raw chickpea flour. In contrast, the presence of microwave roasted chickpea flour exhibited a negative impact on slice brightness. This suggests that MRCPF incorporation resulted in larger or deeper crumb cells and a darker interior compared to WF (Sun et al., 2023). Similarly, a recent study observed that bread prepared with roasted wheat flour displayed a lower slice brightness than bread made with non-roasted wheat flour (Germishuys, 2021). The reduced brightness of composite sponge cakes was associated with variations in cell diameters and volumes within the crumb structure of bread made using roasted flour. Furthermore, the lower L^* value of microwave roasted chickpea flour likely contributed to the diminished slice brightness, highlighting its impact on crumb colour and texture. The predicted and experimental values for slice brightness response is well correlated [Fig. 2 (e3)].

Table 4

Optimized formulation for treated and untreated chickpea flour incorporated composite flour based sponge cake using mixture design model.

Optimization	WF	CPF	MRCPF	HMCPF	→Response Values	Specific Volume (ml/g)	Crumb Hardness (N)	Crumb L*	Crumb b*	Slice Brightness	Protein Content	Desirability
Optimized 1	248.500	3.656	54.095	43.750	Predicted	2.320	4.077	76.062	28.983	103.644	10.604	0.894
Experimental	248.500	3.656	54.095	43.750	Actual	2.054 ± 0.02	6.34 ± 0.58	72.52 ± 0.21	28.96 ± 0.06	98.2 ± 0.20	11.17 ± 0.09	
Absolute Prediction Error						0.266	2.263	3.542	0.023	5.444	0.873	

Relative importance for all the ingredients and responses was kept +++.

3.2.5. Mixture design modelling: effect on protein content of the sponge cake

The interaction of independent variables (WF, CPF, MRCPF, and HMCPF) on the protein content of composite sponge cakes is best described by a linear model. The statistical estimates for these models are presented in Table 3, while the regression model for protein content is outlined in Eq. (6). The results are further visualized through 2D contour and 3D response surface plots, shown in Fig. 2 (f1 and f2).

3.2.6. Protein content = 9.396 A + 13.900 B + 13.632C + 13.440 D (Eq. 6)

The presence of chickpea flour exhibited the highest coefficient for protein content, followed by MRCPF, HMCPF, and WF. This higher coefficient value can be attributed to its higher flour protein concentration (Table 1). Chickpea flour, regardless of processing treatments, contributed to higher protein content in composite flours due to its inherently greater protein concentration compared to soft wheat flour. These findings suggest that increasing the proportion of chickpea flour in formulations can significantly enhance the protein content of composite sponge cakes. Similar findings have been reported by (De la Hera et al., 2012; Krause et al., 2022) for wheat-lentil and wheat-pulse composite flour based cakes. The experimental and predicted values for protein content of the sponge cakes response demonstrated a strong correlation with a R^2 value of 0.860 [Fig. 2. (f3)].

The 3D response surface plot (Fig. 2 f2) highlights a ridge of lower protein content extending toward the upper left area of the plot, indicating that formulations dominated by soft wheat flour yield the lowest protein content. Conversely, the highest response values are observed in the upper right region of the graph, suggesting that formulations with a combination of high chickpea flour (MRCPF, CPF, and HMCPF) levels are optimal for producing composite sponge cakes with maximum protein content.

3.3. Model validation

The optimization of composite sponge cake formulation was conducted using treated chickpea flours microwave roasted (MRCPF) and heat-moisture treated (HMCPF) due to their high protein and resistant starch content. The primary objective of the optimization was to enhance specific volume, crumb lightness (L^*), slice brightness, and protein content while reducing crumb hardness. Soft wheat flour and raw chickpea flour were incorporated within defined limits, and mixture design and response surface methodology were applied for optimization (see Table 4).

Four solutions with desirability values between 0.56 and 0.89 were identified, with the highest (0.894) selected. The optimized formulation included 70.85 % soft wheat flour, 1.05 % raw chickpea flour, 15.47 % MRCPF, and 12.50 % HMTCPF. The resulting sponge cake demonstrated comparable specific volume and crumb L^* values to the control, with higher protein content and a softer texture. The sponge cakes developed using the optimized formulation exhibited a hardness of 6.34 ± 0.58 N, falling well within the typical range of 6.61–12.76 N reported for wheat flour-based sponge cakes by Poonnakasem et al. (2016). The slightly lower hardness value suggests a softer, lighter texture, aligning with consumer expectations for high-quality sponge cakes. A simplex-lattice

centroid mixture design enabled precise ingredient optimization, achieving an ideal balance of quality attributes. The low absolute prediction errors (all below 5.5) further confirm the strong precision and predictive reliability of the developed model in estimating the targeted responses.

4. Conclusion

This study highlights the practical advantages of employing a simplex-lattice centroid mixture design, offering an effective strategy for optimizing ingredient combinations. Various combinations of untreated raw chickpea flour (CPF), microwave-roasted chickpea flour (MRCPF), heat-moisture-treated chickpea flour (HMCPF), and soft wheat flour (WF) were explored. A simplex lattice design facilitated 18 experimental runs, with raw/processed chickpea flour additions ranging from 0 % to 50 % and WF ranging from 50 % to 100 %. Physicochemical and texture properties were assessed, and responses were analysed using regression analysis. The results identified the quadratic model as the most suitable for predicting specific volume, crumb colour parameters (L^* and a^*), slice brightness, crumb hardness, and protein content. The optimized sponge cake formulation achieved a specific volume of 2.054 (ml/g), L^* value of 72.52, b^* value of 28.96, slice brightness of 98.2, hardness of 6.34 N, protein content of 11.17 %, and a desirability score of 0.894. This compares to crumb hardness of 6.6 N and protein content of 8.9 % for the wheat control. The recommended ingredient proportions for the optimized formulation were 70.96 % WF, 1.04 % CPF, 15.47 % MRCPF, and 12.5 % HMCPF. The findings demonstrate the feasibility of incorporating chickpea flour into sponge cake formulations without adversely affecting key baking attributes. Such an approach holds significant industrial relevance, facilitating the production of nutritionally enriched sponge cakes while maintaining desirable quality characteristics.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Mehraj Fatema Z. Mulla: Writing – review & editing, Software, Formal analysis, Conceptualization, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Data curation. **Ewen Mullins:** Project administration, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Richard Lynch:** Funding acquisition, Writing – review & editing, Project administration. **Eimear Gallagher:** Conceptualization, Supervision, Project administration, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Methodology.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lwt.2025.118206>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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